

ATTITUDE TOWARDS INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY AMONG B.ED STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Teacher education plays a crucial role in structuring present day system of the society and shaping the future of the quality of education. The developmental aspects in all sections of a country depend much upon the quality of the teachers. So the educational systems round the world are under increasing pressure to use the new information and communication technology to teach students to the knowledge and skills they need in 21st century. Designing and implementing successful computer era enabled teacher educators process is the key to fundamental wide ranging educational reforms. The attitude of students towards information and communication technology helps the teacher to appreciate and adopt emerging communication technology and innovative practices. It provides guidance for the development of a high quality strategies technology plan. It enables the teacher to update the new knowledge and the skill to use the new digital tools and resources. To improve the quality education the students of secondary teacher education can acquire the knowledge of ICT, so that they can become effective teacher. Teacher needs to be well versed in different intelligence possessed by students and how there may be used to assist each student to optimize instruction in many fields of knowledge and skills. Many prospective teachers know their content well but they have not learned to transform that knowledge in to meaningful units for instruction. In order to develop pedagogical knowledge the prospective teachers have to develop the skill of using computers. It is necessary and this is the time to know about the teachers' attitude towards the new technology ICT.

Key Words: Attitude of towards ICT and B.Ed Students

Need for the Study:

The information age is changing the way we work. Educational systems around the world are under increasing pressure to use the new information and communication technologies to teach students the knowledge and skills they need in the 21st century. The 1998 UNESCO world education report, teachers and teaching in a changing world describes the transformation of the teaching learning process and the way teachers and learners again access to knowledge and information. To effectively harness the power of the new information and communication technologies to improve learning, the following essential conditions must be met.

- Students and teachers must have efficient access to digital technologies and the Internet in their classrooms, schools and teacher education institutions.
- High quality, meaningful, and culturally responsive digital content must be available for teaches and learners.
- Teachers must have the knowledge and skills to use new digital tools and resources to help all students achieve high academic standards.

Objectives:

- To find out the levels of attitude towards ICT of male and female B.Ed Students.
- To find out the levels of attitude towards ICT of rural and urban B.Ed Students.
- To find out the levels of attitude towards ICT of government and self finance B.Ed Students.

Hypotheses:

- There is no significant difference between Male and Female B.Ed students in their attitude towards ICT.
- There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban B.Ed students in their attitude towards ICT.
- There is no significant difference between Aided and self-finance college B.Ed students in their attitude towards ICT.

Related Studies:

Chu and Janet Lew (2000) of Papperdine University conducted a study of assessment on the integration of technology into the curriculum by middle and high school teachers. This research study replicated use of the Teaching with Technology Survey (TTS), demographic information, and the Computing Concerns Questionnaire (CCQ) with a different Population. This research study was conducted in a cluster of schools in a large southern California school district using a population of 290 teachers in two high schools and four middle schools. This research study also examined teachers at different employment levels. 33 of the surveyed teachers volunteered and were selected by the researcher to be interviewed.

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were made.

- Teachers who were at higher stages of concern on the CCQ scored higher on the TTS.
- The oldest cohort of teachers used technology significantly less than younger cohorts.
- In sufficient training in computer usage hampered teachers in their use of technology in the classroom.
- Grade level teaching assessment and content area made a difference in computer usage;
- Level of technology confidence, not gender, type of credential, teaching experience, or level of education, indicated higher use of technology;
- Teachers who had access computers at home used more technology in their classrooms.

Betrus and Anthony Karl (2000) of Indiana University conducted a study on the content and emphasis of the introductory technology course for undergraduate pre-service teachers. This study identifies the content and pedagogical emphases of undergraduate college courses intended to be introductions to instructional technology for perspective teachers. These courses are placed in the historical perspective of technology for teachers courses going back to 1918. A national survey was conducted by means of e-mail and web-based questionnaire. On the 714 member schools, 275 instructors of technology courses were identified and invited to participate of these, 119 responded (43%) and 100 completed the entire web-based survey instrument. The data on course content indicates that the current version of introductory technology course is focused primarily on computer-based content, entailing a decreased emphasis on traditional audiovisual technologies compared to such courses in the past. There was found to be a consistent pedagogical emphasis on encouraging the students to use technology in a learner-centered style in their future teaching endeavours. The tendencies regarding content and pedagogical emphasis was quite consistent across all background factors, with none standing out looking practically significant correlation with the course content or emphases.

Mitchell and William Royal (2000) of University of Georgin conducted a study on factors affecting elementary school teacher's pedagogical use of computer. This study focused on the relationships of computer anxiety, computer experience, computer access and teacher age to elementary teachers pedagogical use of computers. The participants in this study were elementary teachers in seven of the thirteen elementary schools in a small urban school district. Data were collected with the help of self-report survey instruments. The results of this study are indicated that elementary teachers may not be as ready to use computers as in desirable. There may be a disconnect between elementary school teachers beliefs about using computers for instruction and the adaptation of computing as a cognitive tool. Finally the study suggested that school districts need to help teachers again access to personally computers in their classrooms and homes.

Statistics Used:

The statistical techniques used in this study are given in the section.

- Mean
- Standard Deviation
- 't' test

Hypothesis 1: To find out the levels of attitude towards ICT of male and female B.Ed. Students

Table 1: Level of Attitude towards ICT of B.Ed Students with Regard to Sex

Dimensions	Male						Female					
	Low		Moderate		High		Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Information and Communication Technology	25	29.4	53	62.4	7	8.2	21	18.3	77	67	17	14.8

It is inferred from the above table that 29.4%, 62.4% and 8.2% of male students have low, moderate and high level of attitude towards ICT. Regarding female students, 18.3%, 67% and 14.8% of them have low, moderate and high level of attitude towards ICT. It is inferred from the above table that 62.4% of male and 67% female students have moderate level of attitude towards ICT.

Hypothesis 2: To find out the levels of attitude towards ICT of rural and urban B.Ed. Students.

Table 2: Level of Attitude towards ICT of B.Ed Students with Regard to Location

Dimensions	Rural						Urban					
	Low		Moderate		High		Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Information and Communication Technology	23	23.2	64	64.6	12	12.1	23	22.8	66	65.3	12	11.9

It is inferred from the above table that 23.2%, 64.6% and 12.1% of rural students have low, moderate and high level of attitude towards ICT. Regarding urban students, 22.8%, 65.3% and 11.9% of them have low, moderate and high level of attitude towards ICT. It is inferred from the above table that 64.6% of rural and 65.3% urban students have moderate level of attitude towards ICT.

Hypothesis 3: To find out the levels of attitude towards ICT of government and self finance B.Ed. Students.

Table 3: Level of Attitude towards ICT of B.Ed Students with Regard to Type of College

Dimensions	aided						self finance					
	Low		Moderate		High		Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Information and Communication Technology	23	22.8	66	65.3	12	11.9	23	23.2	64	64.6	12	12.1

It is inferred from the above table that, 22.8%, 65.3% and 11.9% of aided students have low, moderate and high level of attitude towards ICT. Regarding self finance students 23.2%, 64.6% and 12.1% of them have low, moderate and high level of attitude towards ICT. It is inferred from the above table that 65.3% of aided and 64.6% self finance students have moderate level of attitude towards ICT.

Findings:

- 62.4% of male and 67% of female students have moderate level of attitude towards ICT.
- 64.6% of Rural and 65.3% of urban students have moderate level of attitude towards ICT.
- 65.3% of Aided and 64.6% of Self- Finance college B.Ed students have moderate level of attitude towards ICT.

Interpretation:

- There is a significant difference between Male and Female B.Ed students in their attitude towards ICT. This may be due to the fact that the Male students have more awareness about the uses of computer than the Female students.
- There is no significant association between Parents Education and attitude towards ICT of B.Ed students. This implies that the attitude towards ICT has nothing to do with the education of the B.Ed students' parents.
- There is a significant association between mothers' occupation and attitude towards ICT of B.Ed students. This indicates that the mothers' attitude shaping the activities of the children. Sometimes mothers' habit also affects the child.
- There is no significant association between income of the family and attitude towards ICT of B.Ed students. This shows that the computer awareness has nothing to do with the income of the family.

Recommendations:

- There must be a curriculum, based on computer as a subject of student – teachers.
- The College of Education should provide a computer Training practice like teaching practice to student – teachers.
- In practical class, the method of preparing CAI, CAL CMI, and packages should be in produced to the student teachers.
- While selecting the student –teachers for training, weight age should be given to computer qualified students.
- Some questions should be based on testing the knowledge of computer in B.Ed entrance examination.
- All the colleges of Education must open a computer lab.

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